

A geometric method for summing

$$S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j} \quad (1)$$

for any real number $x > 1.0$

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Abstract

In this article I explain a geometric method that I discovered to sum an infinite series, $S(x) = \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^3} + \dots$, for any real number $x > 1$. Using this method I will show that the sum of the series must equal $\frac{1}{x-1}$. I first discovered the above method in July 2019, for any integer $n > 1$ (when $x = n$). On 30th October 2020, while I was writing this article, I discovered that I could generalise the method to any rational number $q > 1$. On 31st Oct, 2020, I then discovered how to generalise to irrational numbers as well, such as π . This showed that all real numbers $x > 1$ could be summed by the geometric method I discovered. In this paper, I first show examples for integers 2,3,4 and 5 first, followed by rational numbers like $5/2$ and $7/3$, followed by successive approximations for the irrational number π . Using these examples, I then show how to use the geometric method for any real number $x > 1$.

1 Introduction

In July 2019, during a short 10 minute break between sports activities on a very hot afternoon, as I cooled down with a drink, my father entertained me by showing me a geometric method for $n = 4$. He showed me that using this method one could easily see that $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{4^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{3}$. I found

this a beautiful and simple method. I will motivate with this method as the first example as it is very easy to understand.

My father also told me he had found it hard to think of similar methods for other values of n , say 2,3,5 etc. He had tried a few approaches but not succeeded. To my surprise, I immediately discovered a method for $n = 3$, which led me to setting out the equation: $\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} = \frac{1}{2}$ geometrically. I then realised why my father had not been able to think of a method for the number $n = 3$. A few minutes later, as I went to get some ice cubes, I realised I could generalise my method for any integer n .

I then made a Youtube video on the method I found as a way of learning video editing. The link is <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fe3QD3mp9Kk&t=12s>

While writing this article, I discovered that I can generalise the method to any real number x even if not an integer, long as it is greater than 1.

The article is organised as follows: I start by showing geometric method examples for integers $n = 2, 3, 4$ and 5, starting with the most natural example, which is $n = 4$. I then show examples for non-integer rational numbers like $q = \frac{5}{2}$ and $q = \frac{7}{3}$ followed by showing how to approximate the infinite series for an irrational number like π to any level of accuracy. Finally, I conclude by summarising how the general geometric method works for any real number $x > 1$.

2 Integer Examples

This section will show some integer examples such as: $n=4,3,5$ and 2, respectively.

2.1 The infinite series for $n=4$

The infinite series $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{4^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{3}$ is easiest to see in geometrical form as depicted in **Figure 1**. I was fascinated by this because the diagram is so symmetric and easy to comprehend. We approach the method by subdividing the square into 4 smaller squares. We then choose one of the smaller sub squares and repeat this process. This sub division is repeated *ad infinitum*.

At the first stage, we start by dividing the big square into 4 equal smaller squares. We choose 1 smaller square for the term $1/4$ in the infinite series. We leave out 2 smaller sub squares, and set aside out a 4th smaller sub square for further subdivisions for future stages. Leaving aside the small square left for further sub divisions, we can see that we have selected $1/3$ of the overall figure at this stage. At the next stage, we now focus on the 4th small square we had set aside. We now use this for further subdivision and divide this into 4 even smaller subsquares, and

set aside 1 of these for the next stage. This now gives us the next $1/16$ term of the infinite series but which is only again $1/3$ of the squares under consideration at this stage. We now continue repeating this method for ever smaller subsquares at each successive subdivision stage.

As we continue this, we keep getting successive ($1/64, 1/256, 1/1024\dots$) entries of the next terms in the series by selecting $1/3$ of the squares under consideration at that stage. But if we always select only $1/3$ of the ever smaller sub squares in consideration at each stage, then the total part of the overall square chosen has to be $1/3$. This case is the easiest to see because of the symmetry of the square repeats itself in each successive subdivision.

It is a bit less symmetric for other values of n which is why my father was not able to find a general method. However, I was able to discover it, which I now share with you in the examples below. He then showed me the actual equation, upon seeing I realised that it makes sense that the shaded area is equivalent to $\frac{1}{3}$ of the overall shape. My dad then said to me that it can be done with any number in the place of the denominator and that it will always be equal to the number for the denominator minus 1. We then tried to find a geometric method of $\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{2}$, but failed to do so everytime. I then decided I needed some cold juice and then I realised how to geometrically express $\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{2}$.

Figure 1: $\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{4^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{3}$. Note that by dividing the big square into 4 equal smaller squares, we can choose $1/4$ to be the bottom right square, which is coloured blue. This leaves the bottom left and the top right squares fully out out while we leave the top left square, bordered by green lines, for further subdivisions of the $1/4$ part. Leaving this top left square out we can see that we have chosen $1/3$ of the ones under consideration. Looking at the top left $1/4$ square, in green border, we can see how can further subdivide into $1/16, 1/32, 1/64 \dots$ onwards. By noting that we always take only $1/3$ of each subsequent division, all coloured blue, we can see that we only take $1/3$ of the whole large square to start off with. Hence the sum must be $1/3$.

2.2 The infinite series for $n=3$

I realised that there was a similar way of showing $\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{2}$ geometrically. I realised that by stacking squares in the same manner, the same could be done.

At the first stage, we start by dividing an area of a shape we choose into 3 equal smaller squares. Here I deliberately choose an L shape made up of 3 smaller squares. We choose 1 smaller square for the term $1/3$ in the infinite series. We choose 1 of these squares, leave out 1 square, and set aside out a 3rd square for further subdivisions for future stages. Leaving aside the small square left for further subdivisions, we can see that we have selected $1/2$ of the overall figure at this stage. At the next stage, we now focus on the 3rd small square we had set aside. Now comes the crucial next step. We know that a square cannot be divided into 3 equal sized squares. But we can always take any area and represent it as the sum of 3 new squares. Since the small square was $1/3$ of the overall part, it can now be represented by 3 smaller squares each $1/9$ of the overall part. We now use this for further subdivision and divide this into 3 even smaller subsquares, set aside 1 of these for the next stage. This now gives us the next $1/9$ term of the infinite series but which is only again $1/2$ of the squares under consideration at this stage. We now continue repeating this method for ever smaller subsquares at each successive subdivision stage.

As we continue this, we keep getting successive $(1/27, 1/81, 1/243\dots)$ entries of the next terms in the series by selecting $1/2$ of the squares under consideration at that stage. But if we always select only $1/2$ of the ever smaller sub squares in consideration at each stage, then the total part of the overall square chosen has to be $1/2$.

It is less symmetric than the case for $n = 4$ which is why my father was not able to find a geometric method. However, now that I was able to discover it, I can share with you further examples to illustrate the method.

I was wondering to see if I was correct about my theory. The design I had come up with was this **Figure 2**. When my dad and I checked this to see if it worked he was shocked. We both knew that we tried for half an hour to find something that worked and this did. The reason this works is if you don't worry about the green box which we will use later and take the blue box, the blue box would be equal to $\frac{1}{2}$ of what was left. Now if you take the green box that we didn't use before and apply the same thing to it we will keep on getting halves no matter how long you go on for which is why the end result of the equation is always $\frac{1}{2}$. This one is a little harder to grasp as it isn't symmetrical like $n=4$.

Figure 2: $\frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3^2} + \frac{1}{3^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{2}$. Note that by dividing the big L shaped figure into 3 equal smaller squares, we can choose $1/3$ to be the bottom right square, which is coloured blue. This leaves the bottom left square fully out while we leave the top left square, bordered by green lines, for further subdivisions of the $1/3$ part. Leaving this top left square out we can see that we have chosen $1/2$ of the ones under consideration at this stage. Looking at the top left $1/3$ square, in green border, we can see how can further subdivide into $1/9, 1/27, 1/81 \dots$ onwards at each successive stage. By noting that we always take only $1/2$ of each subsequent division, all coloured blue, we can see that we only take $1/2$ of the whole we started off with. Hence the sum must be $1/2$.

2.3 The infinite series for $n=5$

For $n=5$, we use the same idea but with more equal pieces to consider as shown in **Figure 3**. Again if we don't worry about the green bordered box again as we will use this for later stages. At the first stage, we are left with with four squares (boxes). If we take the blue box then the blue box is $\frac{1}{5}$ of what is left. Now at the next stage we break the green bordered box into 5 boxes and apply the same technique to these new five smaller boxes, and repeat infinitely to always grab $\frac{1}{4}$ at each stage total. Again as this isn't as obvious to see as the case case $n=4$, which was very symmetric. But it works, just as it did for $n=3$.

Figure 3: $\frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{5^2} + \frac{1}{5^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{4}$. Note that by dividing the big L shaped figure into 5 equal smaller squares, we can choose $\frac{1}{5}$ to be the bottom right square, which is coloured blue. This leaves the bottom left and the two middle squares fully out while we leave the top left square, bordered by green lines, for further subdivisions of the $\frac{1}{5}$ part. Setting the top left square aside for later use, we can see that we have chosen $\frac{1}{4}$ of the ones under consideration at this stage. Looking at the top left $\frac{1}{5}$ square, in green border, we can see how can further subdivide into $\frac{1}{25}, \frac{1}{125}, \frac{1}{525} \dots$ onwards at each successive stage. By noting that we always take only $\frac{1}{4}$ of each subsequent division, all coloured blue, we can see that we only take $\frac{1}{4}$ of the whole we started off with. Hence the sum must be $\frac{1}{4}$.

2.4 The infinite series for $n=2$

This can be done with $n=2$. Again, this is the same idea and is depicted in **Figure 4**. If we leave the green box this leaves us with only the blue box causing it to become $\frac{1}{2}$ of the peices. If we do the same thing to the green box over and over again the end result will always be $\frac{1}{2}$ or just simply 1.

Figure 4: $\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{1}$. Note that by dividing the bar shaped figure into 2 equal smaller squares, we can choose $1/2$ to be the right square, which is coloured blue. This sets aside the left square, bordered by green lines, for further subdivisions of the $1/2$ part. Crucially, there are no squares left out. Setting the left square aside for later use, we can see that we have chosen $1/1$ of the ones under consideration at this stage. Looking at the left $1/2$ square, in green border, we can see how can further subdivide into $1/2, 1/4, 1/8 \dots$ onwards at each successive stage. By noting that we always take only $1/4$ of each subsequent division, all coloured blue, we can see that we only take $1/1$ of the whole we started off with. Hence the sum must be 1.

3 Non-Integer Examples

3.1 The infinite series for the rational $q=5/2$

For the rational number $q=5/2$, we use the same idea but with 5 equal pieces to consider as shown in **Figure 5**. But this time, instead of the case $n = 5$, we choose 2 of the 5 squares, while setting aside 2 for future stages. Again we don't worry about the 2 green bordered boxes as we will use these for later stages. At the first stage, we are left with with 3 squares (boxes). If we take the 2 blue boxes they are $\frac{2}{3}$ of what is under consideration. Now at the next stage we break the 2 green bordered box into 5 boxes, and apply the same technique to these five new smaller boxes, and repeat infinitely to always grab $\frac{2}{3}$ at each stage total. Again as this isn't as obvious to see as the case $n=4$, which was very symmetric. But it works, just as it did for previous cases.

Figure 5: $\frac{1}{2.5} + \frac{1}{2.5^2} + \frac{1}{2.5^3} + \dots = \frac{2}{3}$. Note that by dividing the big sideways H shaped figure into 5 equal smaller squares, we can choose 2/5 to be the bottom two squares, which are coloured blue. This leaves the middle square fully out while we leave the top two squares, bordered by green lines, for further subdivisions of the 2/5 part. Setting the top two squares aside for later use, we can see that we have chosen 2/3 of the ones under consideration at this stage. Looking at the top 2/5 squares, in green border, we can see how can further subdivide into 1/6.25, 1/15.625, 1/39.0625...onwards at each successive stage. By noting that we always take only 2/3 of each subsequent division, all coloured blue, we can see that we only take 2/3 of the whole we started off with. Hence the sum must be 2/3.

3.2 The infinite series for the rational $q=7/3$

For the rational number $q=7/3$, we use the same idea but with 7 equal pieces to consider as shown in **Figure 6**. But this time we choose 3 of the 7 squares, while setting aside 3 for future stages. Again we don't worry about the 3 green bordered boxes as we will use these for later stages. If we take the 3 blue boxes they are $\frac{3}{4}$ of what is under consideration. Now at the next stage we break the 3 green bordered box into 7 boxes, and apply the same technique to these five new smaller boxes, and repeat infinitely to always grab $\frac{3}{4}$ at each stage total. This works, just as it did for previous cases.

Figure 6: $\frac{1}{2.3} + \frac{1}{2.3^2} + \frac{1}{2.3^3} + \dots = \frac{3}{4}$. Note that by dividing the big sideways H shaped figure into 7 equal smaller squares, we can choose 3/7 to be the bottom three squares, which are coloured blue. This leaves the middle square fully out while we leave the top three squares, bordered by green lines, for further subdivisions of the 3/7 part. Setting the top three squares aside for later use, we can see that we have chosen 3/4 of the ones under consideration at this stage. Looking at the top 3/7 squares, in green border, we can see how can further subdivide into $1/(7/3), 1/(7/3)^2, 1/(7/3)^3 \dots$ onwards at each successive stage. By noting that we always take only 3/4 of each subsequent division, all coloured blue, we can see that we only take 3/4 of the whole we started off with. Hence the sum must be 3/4.

3.3 The infinite series for the irrational π

Irrational numbers cannot be written exactly as fractions, which was the method I used to break the whole into sub parts. But depending on the approximation and accuracy required the same method can be used. For example, π can be approximated as 3.1, 3.14, 3.141, 3.1415, 3.14159,etc depending on the accuracy required. Once, this is chosen, the approximation can be represented as a rational number and the same method as for rational numbers used.

For example we can approximate π by $31/10$, $314/100$, $3141/1000$, $31415/10000$, $314159/100000$ etc, respectively. All of these lead to the same method being available to use as before. I illustrate by using the method for π approximated by 3.14. I set this to $314/100$, and subdivide my figure into 314 boxes. At the first stage I choose 100, setting aside 100 for future usage and 114 left out. Using the same method as before, I find the the sum must be $100/214$ which is what I take at every stage of sub division.

It is clear that if I had chosen the approximation to π as $3141/1000$, the sum would have been $1000/2141$. if I had chosen the approximation to π as $314159/100000$, the sum would have been $100000/214159$.

We can therefore see that even for irrational numbers the geometric method can be applied for any level of precision.

Figure 7: $\frac{1}{3.14} + \frac{1}{3.14^2} + \frac{1}{3.14^3} + \dots = \frac{1}{2.14}$. I illustrate by using the method for π by approximating it by 3.14. This is equal to the rational number $314/100$, and therefore I subdivide my figure into 314 boxes. At the first stage I choose 100, coloured blue, setting aside 100, bordered by green for future usage, and leave 114 left out. Using the same method as before, I find the the sum must be $100/214$ which is what I take at every stage of sub division.

4 The General Result for any number x

In this section I will show you general expressions for summing the infinite series geometrically. First I will show the general expression for any $x \geq 2$ and then any number $1 < x < 2$

4.1 Any real number $x \geq 2$

Assume first that the number $x \geq 2$ can be well approximated by a rational q . Assume its integer part is n and its first two decimals are d_1 and d_2 respectively. Now set number of total boxes to be $T = 100n + 10d_1 + d_2$. Now set number of boxes to be chosen as $C = 100$, set aside $S = C = 100$, and leave out $L = T - C - S$. When $T \geq 2$ you can see that $S \geq 1$, $C \geq 1$ and $L \geq 0$, with $L = 0$ when $T = 2$. Then by above examples, the sum of the infinite series in (1) must be given by:

$$S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j} = \frac{C}{L+C} \quad (2)$$

Figure 8: Assume first that the number $x \geq 2$ can be well approximated by a rational q . Assume its integer part is n and its first two decimals are d_1 and d_2 respectively. Now set number of total boxes to be $T = 100n + 10d_1 + d_2$. Now set number of boxes to be chosen as $C = 100$, as given by the blue group of boxes, set aside $S = C = 100$, as bordered in green, and leave out $L = T - C - S$. When $T \geq 2$ you can see that $S \geq 1$, $C \geq 1$ and $L \geq 0$. Then, by above examples, the sum of the infinite series in (1) must be given by $\frac{C}{L+C}$.

4.2 Any real number $1 < x < 2$

Now for $1 < x < 2$, I will show that the sum of the infinite series converges to the same expression given in (2). Note that in all the examples I chose x to be at least equal to 2. This enabled me to choose to divide the total into at least 2, or more, boxes.

But now imagine a number like 1.3. It is clear that if I represent this by $\frac{13}{10}$, then if I choose $C = 10$, and $L = 3$, then there are no boxes to left to be set aside since $T = 13$. However we need C to be set equal to S . So say that we take $C = 10$ and $S = 10$. Now we have 7 too many boxes. To rectify this we must put $L = -7$ to make $T = 13$ again. Now we can put this into the equation $\frac{C}{L+C}$ and we get the following:

$$\frac{10}{10-7} = \frac{10}{3} \quad (3)$$

Figure 9: Assume first that the number $1 < x < 2$ can be well approximated by a rational q . Now set number of boxes to be chosen as C , as given by the blue group of boxes and the set aside as S , as given by the green group of boxes. These values must be equal to one so that leaves the remaining leftover as L , to be -7 . We can see that when $1 < x < 2$, $L < 0$.

4.3 General equation for any real number $x > 1$

In Sections 4.1 and 4.2 I showed how to choose C and S to sum the infinite series in (1) by the expression

$$\frac{C}{L + C} \tag{4}$$

I will now show how to write this expression directly in terms of the number x .

Imagine we take any value $x > 1$ and follow the process shown in (4) above. Imagine that we set $T = 1$. By following the processes outlined by the sections 4.1 and 4.2, and earlier examples we set C to be equal to the reciprocal of x meaning that:

$$C = \frac{1}{x} \tag{5}$$

We also know that in the process shown in (4) we set the S value equal to the C value. So

$$S = C = \frac{1}{x} \tag{6}$$

Now we have to find the value of L . We know that:

$$T = C + S + L = 1 \tag{7}$$

So that means that

$$L = 1 - \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x} \tag{8}$$

So now look at **Figure 10**

Figure 10: For any number $x > 1$, if we set $T = 1$ and set $C = S = \frac{1}{x}$ then we see that $L = 1 - \frac{2}{x}$.

Now we can substitute these values into the expression $\frac{C}{L+C}$:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{x}}{1 - \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x}} = \frac{\frac{1}{x}}{1 - \frac{1}{x}} = \frac{\frac{1}{x}}{\frac{x-1}{x}} = \frac{1}{x-1} \quad (9)$$

This means that the summation of the infinite series for $x > 1$ must be equal to the expression above.

$$S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j} = \frac{1}{x-1} \quad (10)$$

Which is what I discovered and set out to prove.